

COMPARISONS OF JAPANESE AND U.S. CONSUMERS' EYE MOVEMENTS WHEN CHOOSING OVER-THE-COUNTER DRUGS: "NAME AND BENEFITS" VS. "INGREDIENTS AND RISKS"

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ABSTRACT

In Japan, package design of over-the-counter (OTC) drugs changed in 2009 because of changes to the *Pharmaceutical Affairs Law*. The revised *Law* expects consumers to choose an OTC drug at their own risk; for this reason, consumers should carefully read the information on OTC drug packages. The present study examined the eye movements of Japanese and U.S. consumers while choosing an OTC drug, and examined how much attention they paid to each item on the package. The results suggested that Japanese consumers paid more attention to the name and benefits of the drugs, while U.S. consumers paid more attention to ingredients and risks.

Keywords: over-the-counter drug, labeling information, culture

BACKGROUND

An over-the-counter (OTC) drug is a drug that can be purchased without a doctor's prescription. In Japan, the *Pharmaceutical Affairs Law* was revised in June 2009 so as to emphasize "self-medication" and the consumer's "own risk." The implication is that consumers should read drug information on the package carefully when buying an OTC drug. However, our previous study showed that Japanese consumers read risk-related information on the drug package only briefly (Go et al. 2009). The present study examined Japanese consumers' eye

Figure 1. Labeling information on a U.S. OTC drug package

movements when choosing an OTC drug, in order to determine how much attention they paid to each information item on the package. In addition, we compared Japanese consumers' eye movements with those of U.S. consumers, because previous studies have shown cultural influence on visual perception (Nisbett & Masuda 2003; Dong & Lee 2008). Moreover, in the United States, OTC drugs have been sold for 50 years in a manner similar to that in Japan under the revised *Law*; there, the idea of "self-medication" is well-recognized.

METHODS

The subjects were 28 Japanese (13 females and 15 males; 20-39 years old) and 23 Americans (8 females and 15 males; 18-39 years old). None were students majoring in pharmacology or chemistry.

Research was conducted using the eye-movement experiment and questionnaire survey.

- **Eye-movement experiment**

In the experiment, three packages of cold medicine were presented horizontally on a computer display, and each participant was asked to choose her/his favorite drug. Three Japanese cold medicines were presented for the Japanese participants, and three

U.S. cold medicines were presented for the U.S. participants. Eye movements were recorded on a personal computer, with the length of time the participants spent examining 10 items on the OTC package—drug name, ingredients, uses, warnings, and directions, for example (Figure 1). If a consumer viewed the drug name and pharmaceutical company longer than the ingredients, it was surmised that she/he placed more emphasis on the name than the ingredients. In contrast, if a consumer viewed the ingredients longer than the drug name and pharmaceutical company, it was assumed that she/he placed more emphasis on the ingredients than the name. If a consumer viewed the uses and warnings for equal time periods, she/he was assumed to have placed equal emphasis on benefits and risks.

- **Questionnaire survey**

After the eye-movement experiment, a self-evaluation of the consumer's attention and the eye-catching effect of each aspect of labeling information were conducted through a questionnaire survey.

The questionnaire survey consisted of questions such as the following: "In the eye-tracking experiment, to what part of the package of the cold medicines did

Figure 2. Japanese participants' viewing durations for the labeling items on OTC drug packages.

Figure 3. U.S. participants' viewing durations for the labeling items on OTC drug packages

you pay attention?”, “Which three parts of the drug’s package were the most eye-catching?”, and “How did you decide which package to purchase?”

RESULTS

• Eye-movement experiment

For the Japanese participants, the order of items based on viewing duration (longest to shortest) was as follows: drug name($M=5.93, SD=2.29$), sales copy($M=3.64, SD=1.33$), directions($M=2.42, SD=0.95$), uses($M=2.39, SD=1.28$), warnings($M=1.09, SD=1.14$), purpose($M=1.00, SD=1.05$), ingredient($M=0.40, SD=0.50$), pharmaceutical company($M=0.38, SD=0.66$), contact($M=0.25, SD=0.37$), risk classification ($M=0.14, SD=0.38$), net quantity of contents($M=0.13, SD=0.26$), and expiration date($M=0.46, SD=0.13$) (Figure 2). The result of analysis of variance showed a significant main effect of items on participant viewing duration ($F[11,27] = 93.16, p < 0.05$).

For the U.S. participants, the order of items based on viewing duration (longest to shortest) was as follows: warnings($M=6.69, SD=7.14$), drug name ($M=3.71, SD=2.44$), sales copy($M=2.16, SD=1.92$), uses($M=1.33, SD=2.28$), directions($M=1.04, SD=1.58$),

ingredient($M=0.99, SD=1.37$), net quantity of contents($M=0.34, SD=0.49$), purpose($M=0.32, SD=0.45$), pharmaceutical company($M=0.10, SD=0.31$), and expiration date($M=0.10, SD=0.18$) (Figure 3). The result of analysis of variance showed a significant main effect of items on participant viewing duration ($F[9,22] = 14.18, p < 0.05$).

Analyzed next was the proportion of time spent on ingredients to that on name; comparisons were drawn between Japanese and U.S. participants. Among the Japanese participants, the ratio of “ingredients/name” viewing duration was 0.07, suggesting that the Japanese participants viewed the names 15.6 times longer than the ingredients. In contrast, among the U.S. participants, the ratio of “ingredients/name” viewing duration was 0.33, suggesting that American consumers viewed the names 3.96 times longer than the ingredients (Figure 4).

Also analyzed was the proportion of time spent on uses to that of warnings; again, comparisons were drawn between Japanese and U.S. participants. Among the Japanese participants, the ratio of “uses/warnings” viewing duration was 4.10,

suggesting that the Japanese participants viewed uses 4 times longer than the warnings. In contrast, among the U.S. participants, that same ratio was 0.89, suggesting that the U.S. participants viewed the uses and warnings for equal amounts of time (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Comparisons of ratio of “ingredients/name” viewing times between Japanese and U.S. participants

Figure 5. Comparisons of ratio of “uses/warnings” viewing times, between Japanese and U.S. participants

• Questionnaire survey

The result of the questionnaire survey suggested that, in deciding which drugs to choose, the Japanese participants listed the following, in order from most frequently cited to least: uses(N=14), package design (N=11), drug name(N=9), sales copy(N=8), side effects (N=8), directions(N=7), color of drug package (N=6), impact (e.g., font size) (N=6), pharmaceutical

company(N=3), advertisement(N=2), price(N=1), and warnings(N=0) ($\chi^2(11) = 30.76, p < 0.05$).

For the U.S. participants, that ordered list of items was as follows: ingredients(N=7), sales copy(N=6), uses(N=4), drug name(N=2), package design(N=2), side effects(N=2), directions(N=1), pharmaceutical company(N=1), price(N=1), impact (e.g., font size) (N=1), color of drug package(N=1), warnings(N=0) and advertisement(N=0) ($\chi^2(12) = 26.79, p < 0.05$). The results suggested that the Japanese participants paid more attention to uses and package design than on warnings. On the other hand, the U.S. participants paid more attention to ingredients and sales copy than on warnings and advertisement in making their buying decision.

DISCUSSION

The comparison of Japanese and U.S. participants suggested that Japanese consumers place more emphasis on drug name and effects than U.S. consumers, whereas U.S. consumers place more emphasis on ingredients and warnings than Japanese consumers. The results suggested that (1) when Japanese consumers choose a drug, they rely more heavily on names than ingredients, and more heavily on benefits (i.e., uses) than on risks (i.e., warnings); (2) U.S. consumers place more emphasis on ingredients than do their Japanese counterparts, and that they place equal emphasis on risks and benefits. Therefore, it is suggested that, to enable Japanese consumers to inform themselves adequately in making an OTC drug purchasing decision, the packages of Japanese OTC drugs should be designed so as to draw more attention to ingredients and warnings.

REFERENCES

- Kihan Go, Jeong Seo Choi, Shinichi Koyama, Megumi Izumisawa, Makoto Shiragami, Haruo Hibino. (2009) The Effects of Risk Categories on the Consumers' Attention to the Package of the OTC Drugs, The 11th Annual Conference of Japan Society of Kansei Engineering. [in Japanese]
- Richard E. Nisbett, Takahiko Masuda. (2003) Culture and point of view, *PNAS*, September 16, 2003, vol. 100, no. 19, 11163-1
- Ying Dong, Kun-Pyo Lee. (2008) A Cross-Cultural Comparative Study of Users' Perceptions of a Webpage: *With a Focus on the Cognitive Styles of Chinese, Koreans and Americans*, *International Journal of Design*, Vol.2, No.2.